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SPIRITUALITY OF AJANTA MURALS

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Abstract

About fifty kilometers from Jalgaon, in Khandesh, on the side of Aravind, in the last century were discovered the twenty nine rock-cut cave temples of Ajanta. The lonely horse-shoe shaped rock, overlooking a small stream, seems, to have been cut off from the world from early times. It must have been carved into spacious prayer halls, with giant sculptures of the Buddha. And the walls of these temples were entirely covered with paintings. The first impression of what has survived of these of picture gallery of sheer grandeur.

The Buddha had taught the kinship of all living things- human, animal and bird. In fact, it was believed that the enlightened one was himself once a bird, and then an animal, and that he lived through several incarnations to become the Buddha. The legends of these incarnations were woven into the birth-called the Jatakas. On the walls of Ajanta, the heroes and heroines of various Jataka stories appear. They are so skillfully painted that they seem to be living, breathing and acting out their lives. These paintings show a remarkable breadth of vision. The main theme is the pain of life, which is ever present, even when human beings seem to be enjoying themselves.

Ajanta paintings created from the mind of artists

The Ajanta frescoes were not meant to be copies of things seen in nature. The painters created figures through the imagination. Our tradition demanded Dhyanamandira, which means 'mental contemplation, before a picture was painted or a sculpture made'. Apart from his two

eyes, the painter's imagination was the third eye. This view followed from the belief that the mind's eye transforms nature. So through they seem life-like, the figures have been felt and thought out and done from memory charged by the imagination. It is as through the artists became gods and put the sap of life into their pictures. So it seems that the figures are breathing.

Colours were often used to communicate feelings and moods. As the intention was to create harmony in the pictures there is a blending of colours, and the painter's mode the sweeping strokes of rounded forms, rather than Jerky figures in sharp lines. Thus, the lines in the Ajanta paintings have been called 'curvaceous', 'musical', 'rhythmic'. The techniques seems to have varied in the 600 years or more during which the caves were painted. Earlier caves have somber colours and thick lines. Later, the colours became rich, though not bright, the lines became lyrical, curvaceous lines. In the later caves, the colours are softer and the line mannered. The picture is decorative and rather sentimental. Perhaps the princes who were the patrons wanted the painters to show them as possible Buddha.

Different style and different dynasty

In the earlier paintings, (caves 9, 10) there is a great deal of similarity with the forms of the Buddhist sculptures found in Bharhut (Madhyapradesh) and Sanchi (Madhyapradesh) of the second first century BC. They also resemble the sculptures from Amravati (Andhrapradesh) of the same period. The reddish-brown, yellow and green colours are firmly applied, with sure brushwork. It is possible that these are the earliest mature works of Indian painting known to us, though they were certainly not the earliest painted in India because such skill in applying colours and in drawing figures could not have been achieved without generation of part effort. In fact, caves nos. 9 and 10 probably show the continuity of the great living tradition of Indian art of the centuries before Christ which have been lost to us by the decay caused by time.

These paintings were executed when the Andhra Satavahana dynasty of kings ruled in the Deccan, Western and Central India (second century BC to about second century AD). This dynasty followed the Hindu faith, but patronized the way of the Buddha also. Some crisis say there was a long interval of time between the painting of caves 9, 10 and the painted

pillars of cave 10. The halo may have come from the Gandhara images of North West India and Afghanistan of the third and second centuries before Christ. The figures are dignified and there is a greater sureness of brush strokes. These pillars were probably painted when the Gupta dynasty was rising in northern India about A.D. 320. These paintings show great mastery of human and animal forms. The walls throb with life. The episodes of the birth, life and death of the Buddha are presented before us.

Expressions on the figures

The dying princess in cave No.16, showing sorrow in the midst of life is a superb example of realizing the mood of the heroine. The princess is sad because her husband has gone away. It would seem that the warm, rich, sensuous world of Kalidasa's poetry has been rendered in paint. Life is shown tinged with sadness. Joy does not last. Death is inevitable. Cave 1 and 2 are said to represent the Indian king, Pulakesin II of Badami receiving an embassy from the Persian monarch, Khushau Perviz. This event took place sometime between AD 626 and 628. This and some other Persian features, confirm the later date of the paintings in caves 1 and 2.

In cave 1 appear the tender and graceful pictures of the renunciation of prince Sidhartha. The figure of Sidhartha the Buddha to be, is larger than life size. The prince holds a blue lotus in his right hand and he stands in a gentle stoop. His face is full of sorrow. His figure suggests his tragic situation. As a young prince, he had to leave his life of luxury and go in search of the Truth. Although this is a noble painting, the exaggeration of the eyebrows, the almond eyes, as also the finger-nails, already show that the beauty of the prince seems more important to the painter than the deep spiritual feeling evident in the figures in the earlier caves.

In these caves the colours are mellow. Love scenes dominate. The paintings tend to be pretty pictures. At this time Buddhism was under attack all over India. The monks perhaps wished to attract people by decorative, rich figures. There is emphasis on jewellery. The great tradition of Ajanta was obviously in decline after hundreds of years of major achievements.

Creativity of Ajanta Artists

Ajanta wall paintings were not meant to be copies of things seen from the nature. The artists created the ideas from their own mind idea creation depend upon artists concept of God and their spirituality. The another most important factor which prompts the artists to choose their own respective fields of activity is nothing other than their hereditary inclination or proclivity. This phenomenon is conspicuous by its presence in each branch of art. Apart from this, the deep erudition of classical arts and scientific matters is another fact which imparts perfection and greater fulfillment to the creation of arts. .The construction of an idol concerned with the science of music will attain a greater degree of perfection and fullness only if the artists in well-versed in musical arts in postures and gestures, in the instruments of percussion of dance and in various other branches of art and science relevant to his profession. The more each work of art gives an aesthetic appreciation of art to the spectator, the greater the glory and dignity of the creation will be.

Colour

The very oxygen of pictures is the harmonious combination of colours in suitable proportions. This capacity of the artists used to be seen in excellent pictures from very ancient days onwards. It is with the help of colour combinations that the picture artists fulfil the requirement of light dimension in the pictures. The method of drawing the things belonging to the other world with the addition of violent colours into the cool colour combination was found everywhere in the world from ancient time.

Elements of Composition

A picture attains its perfection and completeness, thanks to the harmonious blending and arrangement of the colour and shape of the picture effected by the discription of the artist. Such an achievement is recomplished when the work is bared on the laws of painting and mathematical precision linded down hereditaily when picture creation was modernized. The logical system of symanetry was incorporated into the method of picture making. Leonardo da Vinci very forcibly included triangular and curvilinear system in his picture works. It turned out to be a great inspiration in the world of Pictures.

Besides, the system that Leonardo used and practiced in this method can be called rhythmic lines. This can be accomplished and put into use on the top portion and sul Toundrng areas of the picture figures in agreement with the artists mental discrimination, in all the pictures of good artists, originality and naturality can be witrnered in the case of harmonious and balanced mass. The dramatic effect found in the Indian Pictures is quite different from the other pictures of the world. The Indian pictures may be concerned with the scenes token from the field, the mythologiëal stories and so on. But in all the pictures, a peculiar kind of dramatic temperament and attitude can be seen, in all the picturisation like the pictures of Narasimha, Saktipanchaksari etc.

These peculiarities and characteristics can be noticed. The artists are making such dramatic effects in the pictures with a view to capturing the long attentions of the spectators who come to view the picture. Art and life in India are inextricably intertwined. A story in the vishnudharmottara expresses the interconnectivity of the arts in no uncertain terms.j A king called Vajra, a pious and devout man, went to the great sage Markandeya with a request, ‘Oh master, grant me but one with!’ begged the king. “Teach me the art of iconography so that I may make an idol for worship.” Touched by appeal, sage Markandeya was forced to query him a few questions, ‘Do you know how to paint?’ asked the sage.

The king did not, but requested that he may be taught the art if it was a pre-requisite to sculpture. ‘But for that you need to know how to dance’, continued the sage. To learn dancing, the king required a rudimentary knowledge of instrumental music, which needed a foundation in vocal music. Thus, the king had to begin with the octaves to transform his creative potential into tangible form. In Indianart, the highest form of abstraction is embodied in music. So close is the association that the different disciplines also share common terminology: the words, *tala* and *laya*. To a sculptor, *tala* means one measure: to a musician or dancer it refers to one beat or its measure.

The Elements of Painting

The Natyashstra, in particular the rasa theory, came to be the theoretical base for all art in India. In approximately the sixth century A.D. the height of the Golden Age of Indian art,

sage Bharata laid down the foundation of the rasa theory in the Natyashastra, a seminal text, often celebrated as the fifth Veda.

Dealing primarily with dance-drama or natya the rasa theory was all encompassing. The Shilpa and Agama texts took the theory forward practically. They provided invaluable insight into the scientific nature of paints and the canons dictating their use and made it clear that different terms were specific to different arts chitra referred to sculpture, chitrardhaa meant relief sculpture, chitrabhasa denoted painting.

According to these texts a chitra or picture has six limbs. Without these no chitra is perfect says the Samarangna Sutradhara of Raja Bhoja (A.D 1010-1053). The six limbs are: Rupabheda, or differences of form: Pramana, proper size: Bhava yojana (which produces rasa) furnishing moods: Lavanya yojana, furnishing beauty: Sarishya, resemblance to reality: and Varnikabhanya, differentiation of colour.

Rupabheda refers to all forms in art distinguished by individual characteristics. Hence, the Shilpa texts invariably describe how figures of men, women, and kings, sages and gods are to conform to the canons. The second limb is *pramana*; where measurements must be appropriate for proportion and symmetry. The third essential factor is Bhava yojana, imparting a *bhava*, or mood, to the figures. The Natyashastra says 'Bhavā is indicated by dristi, and then vibhava (what produces a bhava). Hence, *bhava* and *rasa* really lie in the dristi, or looks'.

The fourth factor, Lavanya yojana, means imparting beauty to the figures. The Vishnudharmottara says, 'A painting which has not the proper position (sthana), or whose rasas are empty to look at and devoid of life-movement (chetana) is said to be inexpressive.' The fifth limb is sadrishya. The sixth limb of a chitra is varnikabhanga, or the differentiation of colours.

In Indian aesthetics, colour was saturated with symbolism. Each colour described a state of emotional being and was ascribed a presiding deity and a specific relevance. The

Vishnudharmottara says the primary colours are: sveta (white), rakta (red), pitta (yellow), krsna (black) and harita (green); another list includes nila (blue).

From the Caves to the Temples

Painting is an old art. Anecdotal accounts suggest it was not uncommon for households to paint their doorways, facades or even indoor rooms where guest were received. Cave paintings from Ajanta, Bagh, and Sittanvasal and temple paintings testify to a love of naturalism in depicting the human form and nature.

That the ancients dabbled in painting is witnessed in the rock shelter and cave paintings of Bhimbetka in Madhya Pradesh. The canvas of the artist unraveled the story of life, describing hunts, marriages, rituals, floods, wars, accessions and conquests..

Technical perfection and metaphysical abstraction in painting is evident at Ajanta. Here we also see the emergence of a style that appears again and again many centuries later. The tendency to draw abstractions from nature in a manner that is both aesthetically pleasing and effective as decorative embellishment. In the illustrated manuscripts the foundation for the Indian miniature, in which the human form become exceedingly stylized.

In the figurative arts, particularly during the first century B.C – A.D., the treatment of the female was opulent. The women were sensuous, with a large bosom, a fleshy and slightly protruding stomach, a curve in the lips, heavy hips and thighs being encircled by a provocatively tied lower garment. The jewellery included strings in the hair and ornate headgear, precious necklaces, hip girdles, armllets, anklets, and finger rings. However, by the sixth century, when the masterpieces of painting at Ajanta were accomplished, a new female body type emerged. Slender, refined, introverted, and stylized, a body type evocative of the Amaravathi narrative panels.

The next significant phase of Indian painting comes at the end of the sixth century during the Chalukyan period at Badami. It has the earliest examples of Brahmanical wall paintings in

India. One observes the between the 13th and 15 centuries, the Jam ppm-leaf miniatures, specifically the Kalpasutra and Kalakacharyakatha, points to the existence of several workshops and styles for the writing and illustration of religious texts. The trademarks of this key atelier were linearity, sharp and angular contours with faces in profile and an elemental colour palette of black, blue, green, yellow, and red. The art of palm-leaf illuminations was labelled patra lekhana in medieval India. Later, a generalized term, pata chitra, was used for painted scrolls and panels and excluded wall paintings.

The works were visually tuned like a 'passage of music'. The first dated palm-leaf manuscript the Pragyaparamita is ascribed through a dated colophon to A.D. 1190. The palm-leaf was replaced by paper as the preferred surface by the 12th - 13th centuries.

Following the decline of the Cholas and Pandyas, the Vijayanagara dynasty rose to power. The Lepakshi Temple built during the reign of Achyutadeva Raya (A.D. 1530 — 1542) was an impressive shrine with an extensive series of exquisite wall paintings, dispersed in broad friezes in the tradition of the Ajanta murals.

REFERENCES

- 1 Binoy. K Behl, "The Ajanta Caves". Thames and hudson, 1965.
- 2 A.Balakrishna Pillai, "Naveena Chithrakala" 1990. Kerala Lalitha Kala Academy
- 3 Ananda K. Kumaraswamy, "Bharatheeya kalakke oramukham", Rainbow Books & publishers Chegannur.
- 4 Albert skra "Painting of India", 1963 The world publishing company.
- 5 Karal Khandalavala, "LALIT KALA"- 1960, Lalitha Kala Academy, New Delhi.
- 6 Jean Clottes, "Cave Art" 2008, Phaiden Press LTD- London.
- 7 Michel Lorblanchet, "Rock Art in the old world" 2001, Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts, New Delhi.
- 8 Marilyn stokstand, "Art History" 2005, Lawrence king publishing LTD, London.
- 9 Anil Baran Ganguly, "Fine Arts in Ancient India", Abhinav publications- New Delhi- 1979.
- 10 Binoy.K.Behl, "The Ajanta Caves" The new American Library of world, Literature, INC 501 Madison Avenu, Newyork 22, Newyork- 1963.
- 11 E.B. Havell, "Art Heritige of India", D.B Taraporevala sons & co. pvt.LTD.Bombay.1

- 12 Drake Pande, “Master piece of Indian Art”, Luster Press- Rdi Books, New Delhi- 2007.
- 13 Dr.Stella Kramrisch, “The Arts and Crafts of Travancore”, Royal India Society, London- 1948.
- 14 Dr.P.V. Ouseph, “Chithrabhsa” Divine Research Centre, Murigoor-1998.
- 15 Partha Mitter, “Indian Art”, Oxford University Press, Newyork- 2001.
- 16 Mulk Raj Anand, “Chithralakshana” National Book Trust, India-1989.
- 17 Benjamin Rowland, “The Ajanta Caves”, The new American Library of world Literature, INC UNESCO-1963.
- 18 K.K.Varier “Chithralakshnam”, DC Books, Kottayam, Kerala 2011.